

NOTES

Synthesis and Infrared Spectra of Some Triphenyltin Azido Complexes

T. N. SRIVASTAVA and P. C. KAMBOJ*

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 29 September 1981, revised 15 July 1982,
accepted 28 December 1982

EXCEPT a mixed complex anion¹ e.g., $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}^-[(\text{N}_3)(\text{NCS})]^-$, there is no report on organotin azido complexes. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to examine the interaction of triphenyltin azide with a number of N, O and S donor ligands, viz., 2-aminothiozole (Atz), 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), ethylenediamine (en), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen), propylenediamine (pn), N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl ethylenediamine (TMEN), tetramethyl piperidine (TMP), antipyrine (ap), N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMA), N,N-dimethyl formamide (DMF), ethylene urea (Eu), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidine (1-Me-2-pyr), 2, 6-lutidine-N-oxide (LutO), 2-, 3- and 4-picoline-N-oxides (2-picO, 3-picO and 4-picO), pyridine-N-oxide (PyO), hexamethyl phosphoramide (HMPA), triphenylphosphine oxide (Ph_3PO), dibenzylsulphoxide (DBSO), dibutylsulphoxide (Bu_2SO), dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) and triphenylphosphine sulphide (Ph_3PS). It is concluded that triphenyltin(IV) behaves as a hard acid since it complexes readily with N and O donor ligands rather than with P and S donor ones.

Experimental

Preparation of compounds: Triphenyltin azide (m.p. 115°) was prepared by reported method² and directly reacted under anhydrous condition with excess of Lewis bases. The yield of the adducts was ~ 70-80%. Physico-chemical measurements and elemental analyses were made as described earlier³.

Results and Discussion

Properties of the adducts: All the compounds (Table I) are well defined crystalline solid except the adducts $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Bu}_2\text{SO}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{DBSO}$ which are viscous masses and fail to crystallise. The adducts are unaffected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture, soluble in common organic solvents and are thermally stable excepting $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{pn}$ which turns black and decomposes before melting. The conductivity measurements at 25-30° (0.76-4.54 mho $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and cryoscopic data indicate their nonelectrolytic and monomeric nature in solution.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE TRIPHENYL TIN AZIDO ADDUCTS

Complex	m.p. °C	Analysis% ; Found (Calcd.)			
		Sn	O	H	N
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Atz}$	67	23.89 (24.18)	50.54 (51.21)	3.74 (3.86)	13.60 (14.22)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{bipy}$	90	20.80 (21.71)	60.90 (61.81)	3.94 (4.19)	13.10 (12.77)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{en}$	135	27.10 (26.32)	52.85 (53.09)	5.04 (5.08)	16.01 (15.48)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{phen}$	124	19.87 (20.16)	60.80 (61.01)	4.22 (4.23)	10.99 (11.86)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{pn}$	210	24.69 (25.53)	55.01 (54.07)	5.49 (5.36)	15.19 (15.02)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{TMEN}$	104	22.89 (23.42)	55.99 (56.69)	5.87 (6.10)	12.97 (13.77)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{TMP}$	180	21.82 (22.32)	59.98 (60.78)	6.36 (6.37)	9.99 (10.50)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{ap}$	123	19.89 (20.51)	59.98 (60.00)	5.01 (4.65)	11.90 (12.06)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{DMA}$	125	24.82 (24.84)	55.06 (55.11)	4.49 (5.01)	12.01 (11.69)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{DMF}$	65	24.87 (25.59)	53.10 (54.19)	4.80 (4.73)	12.35 (12.04)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Eu}$	101	23.99 (24.89)	52.08 (52.71)	4.41 (4.39)	14.70 (14.64)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot 2(1\text{-Me-2-pyr})$	120	19.88 (20.16)	56.93 (56.94)	5.49 (5.59)	12.01 (11.86)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{LutO}$	206	22.99 (23.10)	58.20 (58.25)	4.67 (4.66)	10.88 (10.87)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot 2\text{-picO}$	102	22.80 (23.75)	56.47 (57.48)	4.38 (4.39)	11.15 (11.17)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot 3\text{-picO}$	133	23.02 (23.75)	57.28 (57.48)	4.40 (4.39)	11.12 (11.17)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot 4\text{-picO}$	130	23.72 (23.75)	58.02 (57.48)	4.02 (4.39)	12.01 (11.17)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Pyo}$	94	24.02 (24.43)	56.52 (56.67)	4.12 (4.10)	12.01 (11.49)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{HMPA}$	100	20.87 (20.84)	50.59 (50.43)	4.99 (5.77)	15.03 (14.71)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Ph}_3\text{PO}$	146	18.09 (17.76)	64.90 (64.47)	4.47 (4.47)	6.59 (6.26)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{DBSO}$	viscous mass	19.20 (19.13)	60.89 (61.73)	4.70 (4.66)	6.72 (6.75)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Bu}_2\text{SO}$	viscous mass	21.80 (21.47)	57.03 (56.31)	5.47 (5.95)	8.01 (7.58)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot 2\text{DMSO}$	98	20.97 (21.71)	49.01 (48.17)	4.97 (4.92)	8.04 (7.66)
$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Ph}_3\text{PS}$	160	17.02 (17.34)	61.99 (62.97)	4.40 (4.37)	6.32 (6.12)

Infrared spectra: The azido group displays three characteristic frequencies in the regions 2020-2070 (vs), 1310-1340 (m, w) and 655-665 (w), assigned to $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{N}_3$, $\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{N}_3$ and N_3 bending modes of vibrations, respectively².

N donor complexes: The large negative shift of ν_{NH} from 3400 and 3270 cm^{-1} in free Atz to 3310 and 3070 cm^{-1} in $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{Atz}$ indicates coordination through N atom of the amino group⁴. The ring vibrations present in free bipy at 1580, 1560 and

* Chemistry Department, Bareilly College, Bareilly.

1540 cm^{-1} move to higher frequencies in the complex and appear at 1590, 1580 (sh) and 1565 cm^{-1} , respectively. The bands at 1449 and 1408 cm^{-1} move to 1480 and 1470 cm^{-1} , and a new band at 1330 cm^{-1} (absent in free base) is attributed to chelation as suggested earlier⁶. Similarly, the absorptions at 1608, 1578 and 1415 cm^{-1} in uncomplexed phen show a positive shift to 1620, 1590 and 1430 cm^{-1} in the adduct and a new band at 1140 cm^{-1} (absent in pure ligand) is an evidence of chelation⁶. $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{TMEN}$ shows a positive shift of νCN mode by $\approx 40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ showing $\text{M} \leftarrow \text{N}$ bonding. The presence of coordinated base in complexes of Ph_3SnN_3 with en, pn and TMP is indicated by the distinct negative shift in $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ absorptions as compared to those in corresponding free bases⁷.

O donor complexes containing ($X=O$) ($X=C, N, P, S$): The νCO at 1666 cm^{-1} in the free anti-pyrene undergoes a distinct negative shift and appears at 1610 and 1590 cm^{-1} on complexation indicating coordination through the carbonyl oxygen⁸. The ir spectra of uncomplexed DMA and DMF show intense absorptions at 1633 and 1670 cm^{-1} , respectively assigned to νCO ⁷.

In the ir spectrum of free Eu and 1-Me-2-pyr the νCO appears at 1680 cm^{-1} and 1655 cm^{-1} and shows a negative shift to 1650 cm^{-1} and 1620 cm^{-1} in their respective adducts, indicating oxygen coordination⁷.

A comparison of the ir spectra of all the azido complexes of N-oxide ligands with free bases (viz., LutO, 2-, 3-, 4-picO and PyO) reveals a large shift of νNO band to lower frequency, as the ir spectra of the adducts exhibit νNO at 1215, 1190, 1150, 1220 and 1210 cm^{-1} respectively as compared to its position at 1246, 1250, 1275, 1250 and 1250 cm^{-1} in the free bases. This indicates oxygen coordination in all the compounds⁹.

In the ir spectra of HMPA and Ph_3PO , the νPO occurs at 1218 and 1195 cm^{-1} and undergoes a large negative shift to 1140, 1130 cm^{-1} and 1150, 1120 cm^{-1} in their adducts, respectively indicating $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bonding in the compounds¹⁰.

In sulphoxide complexes, coordination through the oxygen atom is indicated by the lowering of the $\nu\text{S}=\text{O}$ mode of absorption and a positive shift of the asymmetric $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ mode¹¹.

The coordination site in Ph_3PS is the sulphur atom as is evident from the negative shift of νPS from 637 cm^{-1} in the free ligand¹² to 610 cm^{-1} in the adducts.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for facilities for ir and elemental analyses and the U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance to one of them (P.C.K.).

References

1. R. BARBIERI, N. BERTAZZI, C. TOMARCHIO and R. H. HERBER, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1975, **84**, 39.
2. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and S. N. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1480.
3. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, R. C. SRIVASTAVA and MALA SINGH, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1978, **157**, 405.
4. P. P. SINGH and A. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, **27**, 509.
5. L. DORETTI, S. SITRAM, P. ZANELLA and G. FARAGALIA, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1973, **9**, 7.
6. J. R. FERRARO and W. R. WALKER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1382.
7. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Nankodo Company Ltd., Tokyo, 1962, p. 38, 42.
8. A. RAVI, J. GOPALKRISHNAN and C. C. PATIL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 356.
9. J. W. KAUFFMAN, D. H. MOORE and R. J. WILLIAMS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1165.
10. F. A. COTTON, R. D. BARNES and E. BANNISTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 2199.
11. B. V. LEINGME, R. S. RANDALL and J. R. SAMS, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1972, **50**, 3212.
12. J. A. W. DALZIEL, A. F. LECHOLDING and W. E. WATTS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 358.

Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with Some Anionic Schiff's Bases Derived from Furan-2-Carbaldehyde and Some Amino Acids

(Mrs.) P. R. SHUKLA and O. P. PANDEY

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226 007

and

GOPAL NARAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar-470 003

Manuscript received 30 November 1981, revised 4 August 1982,
accepted 28 December 1982

ALTHOUGH the Schiff bases derived from a variety of aldehydes and amines have been studied extensively as nitrogen donors, the compounds of the heterocyclic aldehydes have been comparatively little investigated so far. The present paper records the synthesis and characterisation of some such complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) derived from furan-2-carbaldehyde and three amino acids.

The specific Schiff bases used are furfural-glycine, furfural- α -alanine and furfural- α -valine which have been obtained in solution by stirring one equivalent of the aldehyde with one equivalent of corresponding amino acid at room temperature in methanol for 6 hr. The reaction with the metal salts has been done *in situ* for which the metal salt in methanol was added to the above solution and further stirred for 10 hr. The solid complex separated was filtered, dried and analysed (Table 1). The anion of the ligand may be represented by Structure I.